

ANALYZING FACTORS INFLUENCING SUB-CONTRACTOR SELECTION IN EGYPTIAN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to discuss the factors influencing the process of selecting a sub-contractor in the Egyptian Construction industry. Quantitative and statistical research techniques were utilized. The study was initiated by a literature review to discover the history of the most common techniques for selecting the appropriate sub-contractor. Then, forty-nine attributes were chosen from the previous research to compose the questionnaire, which was sent to ninety personnel registered in the Egyptian Engineers Syndicate. In the questionnaire, the participants were asked to evaluate each factor through Likert item questions from one to five, where one means that this factor has the "least influence" on the selection process and five means that the factor has the "highest influence". The collected data set was statistically analyzed, Through Exploratory factor analysis, it was found that forty-nine attributes can be expressed by nine latent constructs which explain 67.291% of the total variance. These nine factors can be used in any further research to study how these factors can influence the project objectives, generally time, cost, quality, and scope.

Keywords: Egyptian construction industry; exploratory factor analysis; sub-contractor selection.

1 INTRODUCTION

The construction industry in Egypt has grown rapidly in recent years. In 2023, Egypt's construction industry was forecasted to expand by 6.8% year-on-year [1], followed by average annual growth of 7.4% between 2024 and 2027. Currently, the size of the Egyptian Construction

Market is USD 68.5 billion in the current year and is anticipated to register a Compound Annual Growth Rate of over 6% during the forecast period from 2019 till 2028, which makes it the largest construction industry in Africa [2]. The Egyptian government has made huge investments in the building industry to introduce new cities, modernized transportation systems, as well as infrastructure facilities. This recognized evolution increased the scale and complexity of the intended projects.

1.1 The need for sub-contractors

Main contractors need to manage and conduct numerous projects simultaneously and deliver a wide range of scopes in each particular project, usually in a limited time frame. Accordingly, they usually hire sub-contractors to take responsibility for some work package(s) or projects. Also, the increasing complexity of the construction projects, the inability of the average main contractor to afford full-time employment of skilled craftsmen in each of the several specialized aspects needed to complete the construction projects, the infeasibility of main contractors to own, operate, control, and maintain tools and equipment that shall have a limited usage throughout the project, and the ability of sub-contractors to implement the tasks with higher technical knowledge at a lower cost with higher quality than the main contractor lead to the relay on the sub-contractors' [3]; [4]; [5]. A sub-contractor is typically a construction company that contracts with a main contractor to undertake specific work package(s) on a project as part of the overall contract and may supply labor, material, equipment, tools, and designs [6]; [4].

1.2 Sub-contractors Selection process

Sub-contractor performance directly reflects on the project cost, duration, quality, and safety. Sub-contractors handle a major portion of about 85% of all construction projects in the building industry [7]. As a result, the selection phase of sub-contractors shall be done properly based on a scientific basis and minimizing the risks by choosing the most appropriate sub-contractor [8]. However, the traditional and widely-used approach in the construction industry is to select the sub-contractor based on the lowest bid. The lowest bid criterion is a tradition in contract awarding, and it is crucial to introduce the non-price criteria in the evaluation process [9]. Various studies have introduced methods for sub-contractor selection to consider the multi-criteria which could influence the selection process [10]; [11]; [12]; [13]. Thus, there is a need to obtain the attributes that can influence the contractors in the selection of the appropriate sub-contractor.

2 Literature Review

In recent years, the sub-contractor selection and evaluation process has evolved and is no longer based only on a single criterion which typically was the bid price, but multi-criteria discussion models have been introduced, which usually contain both quantitative and qualitative criteria. Therefore, several researchers in the last decades have been involved in studying, identifying, ranking, and prioritizing the most significant attributes and criteria that have a recognizable influence on the sub-contractor selection process [14].

The sub-contractor selection attributes in thirty-eight publications all over the world through the period from 1991 to 2016 was summarized [8]. They concluded that the attributes with the highest frequency were "Price, Experience History, Quality, Technical capability, financial status, Delivery/Duration, Health and safety record, Management, Production and capacity, Reputation, and Location". These factors were used accordingly in a multi-criteria decision-making model namely Additive Ratio Assessment (ARAS) method. A case study in the Russian Federation was conducted based on these factors and the ARAS method, where eight sub-contractors were evaluated. It was found that the lowest bid price was submitted by the sub-contractor with the least score in the ARAS, which reflects that the lowest bid-price criteria may lead to high risk and low performance in the project.

A questionnaire was conducted to find out the feedback of general contractors towards the importance of tender price in the selection of sub-contractors [15]. A set of fourteen criteria was used to build up the questionnaire as follows. One hundred-forty questionnaires were distributed to contractors within the region of England. Forty-three responses were obtained, representing a response rate of 31%. The criteria which got the top rankings were "health and safety, then insurance, price, and past performance". It was concluded that bid-price is no longer the only important factor in sub-contractor selection.

A questionnaire was conducted in which 120 construction companies were invited to participate, with a 58% response rate (total of 83 responses), for the purpose of determining the sub-contractor evaluation criteria in the Egyptian construction industry [14]. The questionnaire consisted of 55 attributes, categorized under 7 groups: "Cost, Quality, Technical Capability, Management Capability, Health & Safety, Reputation, and Time". The collected data were statistically analyzed through a set of descriptive statistical analysis tests. The Overall ranking of the questionnaire results has been developed based only on the criteria Mean and standard deviation, concluding that the most influencing attributes were: "On-time delivery of materials, Failure to complete the contract due to financial problems, Sub-contractor's difficulty in reimbursement, Reputation, and Tender price". Concluding that the cost only can't be a solo prequalification criterion, since Time, Reputation, and Quality shall be considered more important.

Forty-six attributes were collected from previous studies and conducted a questionnaire within 29 experts in the Egyptian construction field [16]. Then, statistical analyses were carried out to find the most influencing factors which were "Flexibility and cooperation when resolving delays, Reputation, delay, Failure to comply with the quality specifications, Quality, Suppliers incompetency to deliver materials on time, Failure to complete the contract, Physical resources, Tender price, Contractor's difficulty in reimbursement, Flexibility in critical activities, and Safety consciousness on the job site". The decision was based on calculating the mean score for each factor, where the factors with the highest mean score were the most influential. The statistical significance of each factor was investigated by calculating the p-value, where any factor having a p-value less than 0.05 is considered a significant one.

Accordingly, previous studies have widely discussed the sub-contractor selection process and the attributes that influence this process. However, the selection process is country-dependent, as the influencing factors can vary according to the nature of the construction industry from one country to another [17]. Even though, the studies concerned with the Egyptian construction industry were limited to some descriptive statistical analysis, such as mean score and statistical significance tests [14]; [16]. That leads to the fact that the Exploratory factor analysis based on a data set collected from a sufficiently random sample of the Egyptian Construction industry will add value to the current results of the already achieved research in the literature. In addition to the fact that the number of criteria used in the subcontractor selection process should be low enough to assure that the decision-makers can easily evaluate all potential subcontractors based on these criteria [18].

3 Research Objective

Subsequently, the main objective of this research is to extract and analyze the different attributes that influence the sub-contractor selection process in the Egyptian construction industry.

To achieve this objective, a set of sub-objectives were identified:

- Review the literature for the attributes that influence the selection process
- Establish a questionnaire to grasp the expertise in the Egyptian construction market (with an adequate sample size)
- Implement Statistical analysis for the collected data set
- Illustrate the extracted factors based on the exploratory factor analysis.

4 Research Methodology

Accordingly, a group of forty-nine attributes, as shown in Table 1, have been selected based on the conducted literature review, and a questionnaire survey approach has been adopted to evaluate the importance of each attribute in the selection process. After collecting the required data set, a set of statistical analysis tests have been carried out, with a final test; the Exploratory factor analysis in order to discuss how these attributes can load into a set of latent constructs that explain the highest possible variance through the data set.

4.1 Procedures of questionnaire

Identification of critical attributes for the study and preparation of the questionnaire is a critical step for the success of the research. A significant amount of effort has been made in the previous studies on the attributes and the criteria affecting the selection of sub-contractor(s). These research attempts resulted in a well-documented and peer-reviewed set of attributes. For this study, a questionnaire has been prepared by incorporating the key attributes reported in the literature. A five-point Likert item questions (1 least influence, 2 low, 3 moderate, 4 high, 5 highest) were adopted where participants were asked to rank the importance and impact of each attribute on the process of sub-contractor selection based on their experience in previous projects. A survey was carried out among ninety professionals registered in the Egyptian Engineers Syndicate to determine the score of each attribute. The minimum size of the sample required from the targeted population was determined [19], as per Equation (1).

$$n = \left(\frac{p*(1-p)}{v^2} \right) * Z^2 \quad (1)$$

where: p: proportion of the characteristic being measured in the target population, V: maximum standard error allowed, Z: z-score, and n: sample size.

The number of contracting firms registered in Egyptian Federation for Construction and Building Contractors (EFCBC) in the year 2022 is 41,593. Out of these contracting firms, 684 were classified as first-class contracting firms -representing the target population- [20]. Hence, p is estimated to be the ratio between the number of first-class contractors to the total number of contractor companies; p= 0.0164. To account for possible errors in the qualitative answers from the questionnaire, the maximum standard error V was set at 5%. The z-score is equal to 2.58 in case the desired confidence level is 99%. By Substituting in Equation (1),

$$n = \left(\frac{0.0164 * (1 - 0.0164)}{0.05^2} \right) * 2.58^2 \approx 43 \quad (2)$$

The minimum sample required was calculated to be 43. The number of respondents was 73, with a response rate of 81.1%.

Table 1: Attributes influencing sub-contractor selection

Major Group Name	Attribute ID	Attribute Name
Financial Capabilities	F1	Financial status
	F2	Method of Payment
	F3	Flexibility in payment terms and conditions
	F4	Bank Guarantee
	F5	Failure to complete contract
	F6	Type, amount of insurance
	F7	Not buying insurance for major equipment and employees
	F8	Responsiveness to warranty issues
Company Profile	P1	Reputation
	P2	ISO certification
	P3	Sub-contractor personality
	P4	Management ability
	P5	Number of winning projects
	P6	Number of projects completed
	P7	Collaboration with other sub-contractors
	P8	Service after work completion
	P9	Similar project experience
	P10	Registered in associations
	P11	QA/QC programs
	P12	Being familiar with the area or being domestic
	P13	Knowledge of construction regulations
	P14	Scale of projects completed
	P15	Relationship with the client, the general contractor, the local authorities
Resources Capabilities	R1	Technology equipment and facilities
	R2	Construction technique
	R3	Creativity and innovation
	R4	Expertise of personnel
	R5	Tool usage habit
	R6	Poor competency of laborers
	R7	Energy-saving materials and installations
	R8	Onsite plant maintenance and repair programs
	R9	The contractor's equipment and machinery have full-quality inspection stamps
Tender	T1	Tender price
	T2	Tender quality
	T3	Willingness to tender
	T4	The clarity in the estimated cost of each item (Item bid price)
Risk and Dispute	D1	Suppliers' incompetency to deliver materials on time
	D2	Failure to comply with the quality specifications
	D3	Does the sub-contractor predict possible risks to be able to avoid them
Schedule management Capabilities	SC1	Proposed schedule
	SC2	Flexibility in critical activities
	SC3	Flexibility in the noncritical activities
	SC4	Compression of schedule
	SC5	Flexibility and cooperation when resolving delays
Site Management Capabilities	SI1	Safety consciousness on the job site
	SI2	Jobsite cleanliness during projects and upon leaving jobsites
	SI3	Ability to repair on-site and have the facility to maintain machinery
	SI4	Construction waste management regulations
	SI5	Measures to protect the environment, occupational health and safety (HSE)

4.2 Data Analysis

After collecting the data set from the respondents, SPSS software was utilized in order to conduct a set of statistical analysis tests to analyze the data as illustrated below:

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics can be used to summarize data in an organized manner by describing the relationship between attributes in a sample or population [21]. Calculating descriptive statistics represents a vital first step when conducting research and should always occur before making inferential statistical comparisons. Accordingly, the aim of this step was to explore the data set and find insight and trends within the attributes. Table 2 shows the mean score of each attribute, the results of frequency analysis, as well as the relative importance index for each attribute. The "Similar project experience" was recognized as the highest ranked attribute with a mean score of 4.37, followed by the "Reputation" with a mean score of 4.11, and the "Knowledge of construction regulations" with a mean score of 4.04. The "Similar project experience" was the most frequently given score of 5, as the highest influencing attribute, with a total of thirty-nine participants. The "Scale of projects completed" has been the most selected as a high influencing attribute given a score of 4, with a total of thirty-five participants.

4.2.2 The Normality Test

The normality tests are supplementary to the graphical assessment of normality [22]. The main tests for the assessment of normality are Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test, and Shapiro-Wilk (S-W) test, etc. Among the common tests of normality, the (K-S) test is much-used. In this test, the null hypothesis is that "sample distribution is normal." If the test is significant, the distribution is not normal. This means that if the p-value is below 0.05, the null hypothesis shall be rejected, and the data set is not normally distributed. In our study, the p-value using both (K-S) and (S-W) tests are below 0.05 which means that the collected data is not normally distributed. If continuous data follows a normal distribution, then we present this data in mean value [23]. On the contrary, If the data is not normally distributed, the resultant mean is not a representative value of our data, which means that we need a further analysis rather than depending on the ranking of the attributes based on their mean score.

4.3 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Factor analysis is a broad term representing a variety of statistical techniques that allow for estimating the unobserved structure underlying the variations of observed attributes and their interrelationships [24]. Also, the Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is utilized to identify a set of latent factors that reconstruct the complexity of the observed manifest data in a form that the factor solution extracted from an EFA should retain all important information available from the original data while unnecessary and redundant information -as well as noises induced by sampling and measurement errors- are removed.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Attribute Name	Frequency of Selection					Mean
	Least	Low	Moderate	High	Highest	
Financial status	0	4	25	31	13	3.73
Method of Payment	1	9	30	30	3	3.34
Flexibility in payment terms and conditions	0	7	23	28	15	3.68
Bank Guarantee	2	15	24	24	8	3.25
Failure to complete contract	3	7	21	19	23	3.70
Type, amount of insurance	6	11	33	21	2	3.00
Not buying insurance for major equipment and employees	8	15	27	19	4	2.85
Responsiveness to warranty issues	3	6	33	24	7	3.33
Reputation	0	0	22	21	30	4.15
ISO certification	4	20	34	9	6	2.86
Sub-contractor personality	1	7	25	29	11	3.58
Management ability	1	5	16	33	18	3.86
Number of winning projects	1	6	24	28	14	3.68
Number of projects completed	0	2	18	33	20	4.00
Collaboration with other sub-contractors	1	9	19	31	13	3.69
Service after work completion	3	6	21	31	12	3.63
Similar project experience	1		9	24	39	4.39
Registered in associations	3	8	33	24	5	3.30
QA/QC programs	5	13	23	21	11	3.20
Being familiar with the area or being domestic	1	10	25	22	15	3.63
Knowledge of construction regulations	0	2	17	30	24	4.08
Scale of projects completed	0	1	24	35	13	3.85
Relationship with the client, the general contractor, the local authorities	0	2	22	25	24	4.01
Technology equipment and facilities	0	6	26	25	16	3.70
Construction technique	0	4	24	29	16	3.79
Creativity and innovation	2	10	31	21	9	3.34
Expertise of personnel	0	7	25	29	12	3.65
Tool usage habit	4	15	31	17	6	3.06
Poor competency of laborers	3	19	21	20	10	3.13
Energy-saving materials and installations	5	16	24	18	10	3.15
Onsite plant maintenance and repair programs	1	15	28	19	10	3.28
The contractor's equipment and machinery have full-quality inspection stamps	1	19	19	23	11	3.30
Tender price	1	4	16	27	25	4.04
Tender quality	0	6	16	30	21	3.95
Willingness to tender	0	4	31	28	10	3.65
The clarity in the estimated cost of each item (Item bid price)	0	4	25	26	18	3.81
Suppliers' incompetency to deliver materials on time	2	10	18	24	19	3.59
Failure to comply with the quality specifications	1	7	16	25	24	3.86
Does the sub-contractor predict possible risks to be able to avoid them	2	15	22	25	9	3.34
Proposed schedule	1	4	18	26	24	3.99
Flexibility in critical activities	0	9	12	32	20	3.89
Flexibility in the noncritical activities	6	13	37	12	5	2.94
Compression of schedule	1	10	30	23	9	3.38
Flexibility and cooperation when resolving delays	0	7	18	27	21	3.89
Safety consciousness on the job site	2	3	23	27	18	3.74
Jobsite cleanliness during projects and upon leaving jobsites	3	11	27	24	8	3.30
Ability to repair on-site and have the facility to maintain machinery	3	11	24	30	5	3.26
Construction waste management regulations	2	9	20	28	14	3.59
Measures to protect the environment, occupational health and safety (HSE)	4	13	27	18	11	3.23

Mainly, the EFA consists of two main procedures: factor extraction and factor rotation. The extraction of factors involves choosing the type of model as well as the number of factors to

extract [25]. Factor rotation comes after the factors are extracted; the goal of factor rotation is to improve the interpretability of the factor solution by reaching the simple structure [26]. The simple structure aims to achieve the largest amount of variance explained by the extracted factors. For extraction of factors the "principal axis factors" method has been adopted. If the assumption of multivariate normality is "severely violated" it is recommended to use of the principal factor methods; in which one method of them is the principal axis factors [27]. For the rotation of factors, an orthogonal rotation method shall be adopted which assumes that the extracted factors are independent and uncorrelated. In this case, the resulting Simple structure is called the Rotated Factor Matrix, that simply shows how each attribute loads into an extracted factor. First, to evaluate the adequacy of the collected data set for factor analysis, the Kaiser– Meyer–Olkin (KMO) test [28] was conducted. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test of Sampling Adequacy (KMO) is a measure of the shared variance in the items. The value of KMO represents the ratio of the squared correlation between attributes to the squared partial correlation between attributes. It varies from 0 to 1. A value close to 1 indicates that the pattern of correlations is relatively compact and hence factor analysis should give distinct and reliable results. A minimum value of 0.5 has been suggested [29]. In this study, for the forty-nine attributes, The KMO value is 0.601 which is deemed good for this study. Starting the initial step for the EFA using the forty-nine attributes, the first procedure is deciding the rule to follow to get the number of extracted factors. In our study, the K1 - Kaiser's eigenvalue-greater-than-one rule is adopted, as it is the best-known and most utilized in literature [27]. The result for the initial iteration is that the forty-nine attributes load into thirteen factors. But the purpose of this step is to identify variables that have not loaded (in the Rotated Factor Matrix) onto any of the major factors with sufficiently large factor loadings and remove those items [24]. It is recommended to retain items that load clearly and strongly onto one factor while showing small to nil loadings onto other factors. Through investigating the Rotated Factor Matrix (Simple Matrix) and interpreting the Loading factors, a set of five runs were implemented, at the end of each run the rotated factor matrix was judged based on the loading factors for each attributes, where any attribute having a multiple loading or null loading was eliminated. At the end, thirty-nine attributes - that loaded into nine factors, where every attribute was loaded into a single extracted factor. At this point, we can consider the extracted number of factors as the minimum number of factors that can explain the highest possible variance of the data set which represents the forty-nine attribute. The variance explained by the nine extracted factors accounts for 67.291% of the total variance. The variance explained meets the suggested threshold of 50-60% [30].

4.4 Discussion of Extracted Factors

- 1) Technical Abilities: First factor explains 23.916% of the total variance and contains

underneath it seven attributes. Technical capability has been one of the most frequently mentioned factors, with being mentioned in twenty-four articles with a frequency of 63% [16]. This factor describes equipment, tools, and manpower abilities. The first attribute underlying this factor, energy-saving materials and installations is generally believed to be a vital attribute concerning the resource management vision adopted by the sub-contractor, especially with the recent trend of building more and more green and sustainable constructions. The second attribute, Onsite plant maintenance and repair programs are to ensure the machinery resources perform optimally and longevity. This involves a range of activities, such as routine inspections, preventive maintenance, emergency repairs, and equipment replacement. The third attribute, Creativity and innovation represents the methodology for optimizing the use of equipment and manpower by staying in coup with the modern techniques in the construction industry. The fourth attribute, Tool usage habit represents the managerial vision to maximize the usage of equipment and tools available in the construction site, this ability to be in accordance with the skilled labors that can satisfy this vision. The fifth attribute, Construction technique represents the awareness to select the appropriate methodologies for implementing the scope of work under construction. The sixth attribute, the contractor's equipment and machinery have full-quality inspection stamps to make sure that no hazard concerning the safety of the labors nor risks concerning any possible delays could arise. Finally, Technology of equipment and facilities represents the level of modernity of the available equipment and tools in the sub-contractor's hands.

2) Sub-contractor profile: Second factor explains 11.262% of the total variance and underlays nine attributes. The first attribute underlying this factor, being familiar with the area or being domestic, explains to what extent the experience of the sub-contractor is reaching, which reflects directly on the experience level of the company [16]. The second attribute, Collaboration with other sub-contractors which correlates with the third attribute Relationship with the client, the general contractor, the local authorities with a correlation coefficient ($r = 0.503$) with statistical significance ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$). Both second and third attributes represent the communication capabilities of the contractor to collaborate and have a long-term relationship with a wide range of project stakeholders. The fourth attribute, Management ability which has been used in fourteen previous articles concerning the criteria for sub-contractor selection [8]. The fifth attribute, Expertise of personnel which considers the years of experience of the sub-contractor staff members, and any additional certifications they might hold. The sixth attribute, Number of projects completed. The seventh attribute, Reputation which has been believed to be one of the highly ranked criteria [14]. The eighth attribute, registered in associations such as the EFCBC, which puts restrictive acceptance criteria for acceptance, in accordance with being registered in such reputable associations shall give credits and advantage in bidding competition. The ninth attribute, Knowledge of construction regulations which include the

standards and codes that regulate the construction process in the country.

3) Competency: Third factor explains 6.312% of the total variance and underlays four attributes. The first attribute underlying this factor is Poor competency of laborers which evaluates the experience and qualifications of the sub-contractor crew. The second attribute, Failure to complete the contract, represents the percentage of projects that the sub-contractor failed to finalize or achieve its objectives. The third attribute, incompetency to deliver materials on time, represents the ability of the sub-contractor to handle procurement-related issues properly. The fourth attribute, Failure to comply with the quality specifications, defines the ratio of the non-conforming work implemented by the sub-contractor to the total work implemented successfully.

4) Tender: Fourth factor explains 5.81% of the total variance and underlays four attributes. The tender stage is crucial in the project. Overall tender sum, including the ability to submit bona fide tenders with minimal tagged items, were perceived to be the most influential criteria for the award of a subcontract [7]. The first attribute underlying this factor, Tender quality, is a vital criterion to overcome the barrier of providing better cost-certainty and quality of response in quotations to contractors [31]. The second attribute, The clarity in the estimated cost of each item, refers to the sub-contractor's ability to submit a detailed and transparent breakdown of the costs regarding various items. The third attribute, Tender price, represents the bidding price submitted by the sub-contractor to get awarded by the scope of work released by the main contractor. The fourth attribute, Willingness to tender, measures the reliability of the sub-contractor and the probability that the sub-contractor will complete the project work once awarded the contract [32].

5) Financial references: Fifth factor explains 4.790% of the total variance and underlays four attributes. This factor has been widely discussed in previous publications that handle the criteria of selecting and evaluating sub-contractors, with a total number of twenty articles [8]. The first attribute underlying this factor, Bank Guarantee, represents the document submitted by the sub-contractor to the main contractor to ensure his financial abilities to meet the contractual obligations. The second attribute, Flexibility in payment terms and conditions, illustrates the allowance to negotiate with the sub-contractor about the price of one item or more. The third attribute, Type, and amount of insurance represents to what extent the sub-contractor is protecting himself and related personnel against possible potential risks and losses. The fourth attribute, Responsiveness to warranty issues, refers to the ability to properly and effectively deal with any issues or defects that shall arise after the completion of their scope of work, and during the warranty period.

6) Schedule Management: Sixth factor explains 4.503% of the total variance and underlays three attributes. The first attribute underlying this factor, Proposed schedule, refers to

baseline schedule that the sub- contractor shall submit in the tendering stage for the scope of work under bidding. The second attribute, Flexibility and cooperation when resolving delays, it represents the situation of a delay that needs cooperation from both the main contractor and the sub-contractor and was reported to be one of the most critical attributes [16]. The third attribute, Flexibility in critical activities, concerns the methodology adopted by the sub-contractor to deal with the critical activities throughout the construction stage.

7) On-site Contribution: Seventh factor explains 3.915% of the total variance and underlays four attributes. There is an impact for the sub-contractor's on-site performance on achieving project objectives and the relationship with the main contractor, and the factors that may affect it as well [33]. He concluded that the main contractor has a vital role in enhancing the sub-contractor's on-site performance. The first attribute underlying this factor, Construction waste management regulations, clarifies whether the sub-contractor is familiar with the regulations concerned with the waste material resulting from the construction activities. The second attribute, the ability to repair on-site and have the facility to maintain machinery, concerns the ability to keep the workforce ongoing despite any sudden failures. The third attribute, Measures to protect the environment, occupational health, and safety (HSE), since the sub-contractor is usually a part of the organization in the construction site, he/she shall be working in accordance with the measures and policies concerning the surrounding environment, typically the HSE plan of the main contractor. Health and safety records are considered one of the frequently mentioned criteria in recent publications, being mentioned fourteen times [8]. The fourth attribute, Jobsite cleanliness during projects and upon leaving job sites, discuss the activities implemented by the sub-contractor in the construction site, once finished the scope of work under consideration.

8) Experience History: Eighth factor explains 3.483% of the total variance and underlays two attributes. This factor is the second most mentioned factor in the publications [16], with a total number of twenty-eight. The first attribute underlying this factor, Scale of projects completed, can be expressed at the maximum value of properly executed projects during a certain period of time in millions [14]. The second attribute, Similar project experience, represents the number of analogies projects that have been executed by the sub-contractor. As discussed earlier, based on descriptive statistics, it is believed to be the most influential attribute in the selection process.

9) Financial Status: Ninth factor explains 3.301% of the total variance and underlays two attributes. This factor has been mentioned twenty times in publications [16], with a frequency of 53%. The first attribute underlying this factor, the Method of Payment, represents the proposed payment plan requested by the sub-contractor. The second attribute, Financial status, Many studies have used this attribute to express the amount of work done in the last five years [34].

4.5 Mathematical validity of factor analysis

After carrying out the exploratory factor analysis and settling on the extracted factors, it is important to double check if factor analysis measured what was intended to be measured, which means to ensure that the attributes in each factor formed collectively explain the same measure within target dimensions [35]. If attributes truly form the factor identified, it is expected that they shall have a reasonable extent of correlation with one another but not the perfect correlation though. By calculating Spearman correlation coefficients (Since the attributes are not normally distributed) using SPSS we can estimate the extent of correlation among various attributes. The values of Spearman correlation coefficients for the attributes loading into the technical abilities factor are tabulated in Table 3. It is found that Spearman bivariate correlation coefficients are greater than 0.30 in most of the cases among different attributes in all the factors. From these results, we can ensure that factors formed in factor analysis contain attributes that are related.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix For Attributes Of Factor (1)

Attributes ID	R1	R2	R3	R5	R7	R8	R9
R1	1.000	0.496	0.297	0.251	0.227	0.406	0.422
R2		1.000	0.336	0.356	0.358	0.418	0.416
R3			1.000	0.438	0.467	0.419	0.424
R5				1.000	0.526	0.358	0.385
R7					1.000	0.724	0.431
R8						1.000	0.520
R9							1.000

5 Conclusion

This research -based on an Exploratory factor analysis- reveals the most critical factors of sub-contractor selection process in the construction industry in Egypt which are technical abilities, Sub-contractor profile, Competency, Tender, Financial references, Schedule Management, On-site contribution, Experience History, and Financial Status. These findings support the findings of various studies [8]; [16]; [14]; [32]; [7]; [31]; [34], these studies have introduced and discussed one or more of these factors as factors that influence the process of selection and evaluation. This research tended to make an insightful overview of the attributes that influence the process of selection of sub-contractors, based on the randomly collected data set within the personnel related to the Egyptian construction industry. The results provided evidence that the Bid Price can't be a solo criterion in the selection process, and the participant provided a higher ranking to attributes rather than the Bid price, as the Similar project experience, Reputation, Knowledge of construction regulations, Number of projects completed, and Relationship with the client, general contractor, and local authorities. The results from this study can be used as an initiation to any further multi-criteria decision model.

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